

Memory

Difficulty
remembering
sign in
information such
as passwords

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Easy to use app?

Help?

Simpler
processes?

Memory

**Difficulty
remembering
personal and
family
information**

Existing tools

**Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...**

What would help?

Easy to use app?

Help?

**Simpler
processes?**

Memory

**Difficulty to
remember
which button
to press each
time**

Existing tools

**Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...**

What would help?

Easy to use app?

Help?

**Simpler
processes?**

Memory

**Difficulty
remembering
processes**

Existing tools

**Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...**

What would help?

Easy to use app?

Help?

**Simpler
processes?**

Memory

**Difficulty
remembering
appointments
and important
tasks**

Existing tools

**Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...**

What would help?

Easy to use app?

Help?

**Simpler
processes?**

Memory

**Difficulty
retaining
information**

Existing tools

**Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...**

What would help?

Easy to use app?

Help?

**Simpler
processes?**

